
COMPARATIVE STUDY OF INTERNAL AUDIT AS AN ACTIVE FORM OF MANAGEMENT CONTROL

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Abstract. *The modern development of market relations in the Moldovan economy has led to the delimitation of different fields of activity, including between the classic and new forms of financial and managerial control. The new economic challenges, together with the use of progressive methods of managing business operations, require the use of those forms and types of control that contribute to a reliable assessment of the company's financial results and financial situation, harmonize consumer interests with efficient use of capital and resources and the creation of conditions for obtaining economic benefits and solving tasks. Currently, one of the main challenges is to move from passive finding control to its active forms, in particular to internal audit, which allows the company's management to be provided with such analytical information that greatly increases the effectiveness of forecasting and justification of organizational and economic decisions. In this regard, based on the understanding of foreign experience, this article will conduct a comparative analysis of two forms of control: passive ascertaining and internal audit as an active form of management control.*

Key words: *audit process, internal audit, financial control, inspection, management.*

In the Republic of Moldova actively run inter-related systems of the state control (inspection), managerial (internal audit) and external ones (external audit) [2, p.251]. Simultaneously, in conditions of integration of productive objects, formation of vertical and horizontal integrated corporate structures, activation of foreign capital, issues of demarcation and rationale organization of the respective systems of control become the most important condition of their functionality, sufficiency and relevance. Nowadays, both for business and state the priority is to fully identify and use reserves available for raising effectiveness of economic activity and raising competitiveness, which can be achieved based

on a detailed elaboration of both theoretical and methodological aspects in line with a generalization of the international experience.

One of the functional forms of the financial and economic control is inspection [12, p.6]. In the economic literature prevailing opinion about inspection is it as being a method of control [7; 11; 12]. However, it is commonly known, that method in philosophical term is a means of getting to know, a means of reaching the aim of research. For a method it is typical studying the manifestations of the economic life, but it does not express contents, aim and tasks. Such a statement is erroneous, given that, being a method of control, the inspection itself cannot have its own issue and method. In this regard, a considerable role plays determination of boundaries and limitations of inspection, to comprise the knowledge about objects of inspection as a whole. As objects subjectable to inspection can be certain branches of an economy, economic processes at the enterprises and in organizations, de facto availability and preservation of various types of property.

The inspection consists in a system of control measures to check-up the legitimacy, correctness and relevance of the operations of a company or organization, as well as actions of an executive [6]. To mention is that, during tens of years among researchers there is a discussion about the limitation of extension of objects, and hence, the subject of. This debate has not lost its actuality up to nowadays. For instance, the european practice considers as actual means of control not only the book records, but also depending on circumstances and accompanying events [7; 9; 14]. We share the stance of those authors, who claim that the controller cannot avail of universal knowledge. In this regard, we consider appropriate the recommendations, supporting that, while performing the control it is necessary to consider only those issues and circumstances, which to a certain extent, are connected with the book-keeping and can serve as ground and object for check-ups, analysis and conclusions inspection [5, p.289]. All the objects of inspection in economy are interrelated, this is why sharing and opposing them can be with a commonly known extent of conditionality. Objects of inspection are necessarily regarded as applicable to specific conditions.

The internal audit is an activity of providing independent and objective guarantees and consulting, directed to improving the improvement of the operations of an economic unit [3, p.16]. In line with that, according to International Auditing Standard **610 “Using the Work of Internal Auditors”**,

internal audit function a function of an entity that performs assurance and consulting activities designed to evaluate and improve the effectiveness of the entity's governance, risk management and internal control processes [10, p.684]. Inter alia, the functions of the internal audit internal audit comprises studying, evaluation, and monitoring of adequacy and effectiveness of the book-keeping systems and internal control [13, p.119].

According to provisions of the **International Standards for the Professional Practice of Internal Auditing** the subject of the internal audit is considered an aggregation of various objects, occurrences and factors, taking place in the managerial process of the entrepreneurial activity, reflected in the system of the administrative and book-keeping control, non-financial documents and systemically assessed in terms of observance of legislation, economic effectiveness of the performed operations, achieved results and targets [1].

Nowadays a demarcation occurs of spheres of activity of the financial control systems, with simultaneous enhancement of interrelationship between them, with the aim of diminishing overlapping in terms of operations and functional directions of activity. In these circumstances, the internal audit should be considered as an element of the internal control system, which is necessary for big economic entities mainly of the private sector of economy, so that by its help successfully compete on the market on the account of enhanced quality, decreased cost of production, knowledge of market demand and, this way, increased effectiveness of the operations [4, p.153-154].

The major advantage of the internal audit consists in its accessibility, fewer costs compared with the external audit, access of these services any time, deep knowledge of the situation by the internal auditors at the company, style of work and management, attraction by auditors of highly qualified professionals of the departments, as well as guaranteeing a permanent observation of legislations [8, p.33-34].

As mentioned above, with regards to the essence of the internal audit there are various opinions. Proceeding from the fact that some authors understand it in narrow and take it for inspection, further in the Table no. 1, there is a comparative description of inspection and internal audit.

Table 1. Comparative characteristics of the internal audit and inspection

Distinctive trait	Form of financial control	
	internal audit	inspection
Aim	Informational supply to the owners in the frame of the enterprise and protection of their patrimonial interests	Informational provision of the supervisory body in the frame of the existent economic system
Subject assessed in terms of performed operations	Assessment of current operations, safety and stability of the enterprise operations	Assessment of the previous activity of the enterprise, execution of planned indicators
Main functions of the controlled	Control and analytical, informational and consulting functions	Control and informational functions
Applied types of check-ups	Applying risk and system-oriented audit	Documentary inspection, random check-ups of assets' safety and credibility of accountancy
Main directions of the check-ups	Inspection procedures, connected to the insurance of asset safety, legal inspection and consulting check-up and consulting on various issues	Control actions, linked with the preservation of actives, documentary and factual inspection of legitimacy and relevance of performed operations
Methodological techniques	Factual, documentary and assessing techniques, directed towards getting auditing evidence and checking-up the assets' safety	Documentary and factual techniques of inspection, directed mostly towards checking-up the safety of the assets
Assessment of managerial activity	Penetration into function of management with subsequent assessment of the management quality and working up proposals on its improvement	Check-up of legitimacy and correctness of executives' actions when performing economic operations
Organization and management of control	Strict regulation of the activity at the organization level and control of the audit quality	Tough centralization and labor discipline, application of Sectorial regulations on performing inspections

Proceeding from the mentioned above, one can state, that the internal audit needs to be perceived broadly, as a managerial function, as a form of internal control, which employs as tools complex inspections, thematic, analytical, thorough and other types of check-ups. In line with this the internal audit does not merely provide for a detailed thorough check-up of the financial-economic and operational activity, but also works up proposals on optimization of the economic

activity, rationalization of costs and raising profits, provides various consulting services for the management [6]. While performing check-ups on various aspects of the operations and competently researching and assessing the work of the enterprise, while stemming on credible information, audit provides the internal user grounded proposals concerning managerial decisions.

In line with that, regardless on the difference between the internal audit from inspection, when deciding on frequent and similar questions, the audit does not overlap but completes the inspection, providing important function for the management. One should also mention that, in line with the mentioned advantages, the internal audit has also several shortages, related with the usage of random method and limitations connected thereto. This does not allow internal audit provide full guarantee, that the book-keeping system and internal audit avoid essential mistakes, that undetected abuses are missing; neither subjects to control the events, which are not registered in the documents, if inspection procedures are missing, which are supposed to provide for complexity of checking-up records.

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